

Stability Constants of 3-Chloro-2-Hydroxy-Butyrophenone Complexes with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II)

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Proton-ligand stability constant of 3-chloro-2-hydroxybutyrophenone and stability constants of its complexes with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) have been determined potentiometrically at 40° ($\mu \approx 0.1M$ NaClO₄) in water-dioxane (25 : 75 v/v) medium. The order of stability constants is found to be Cu > Co > Ni.

IN continuation of our studies on complexes of 2-hydroxyphenones¹, the present paper describes the stability constants of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) chelates of 3-chloro-2-hydroxy-butyrophenone (3-Cl-OHB) in aqueous-dioxane medium containing 75% dioxane by volume and 0.1 M NaClO₄ using Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique as applied by Irving and Rossotti².

Experimental

3-Cl-OHB was prepared as described earlier³. Its stock solution was prepared by dissolving the required amount in purified dioxane⁴ (S. Merck technical grade). Standard metal perchlorate solutions were prepared as described earlier⁵. Sodium perchlorate (Reidel) was used to keep the ionic strength constant. Standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (E., Merck) solution was prepared according to the method of Allen and Low⁶. pH-measurements were made with a Metrohm pH-meter fitted with a glass electrode in combination with a saturated calomel reference electrode. The tiectrode system was calibrated at pH 4.03 with potassium hydrogen phthalate and at pH 9.07 with borax buffers.

The following solutions (total volume 40 ml) were prepared and titrated against 0.4976M NaOH.

(i) 2 ml 0.1555M HClO₄ + 5 ml 0.8M NaClO₄ + 3ml water + 30ml dioxane, (ii) 2 ml 0.1555 M HClO₄ + 5 ml 0.8 M NaClO₄ + 3 ml water + 10 ml 0.0101 M 3-Cl-OHB + 20 ml dioxane; and (iii) 2 ml 0.1555 M HClO₄ + 5 ml 0.8 M NaClO₄ + 1 ml water + 2 ml \approx 0.01 M metal perchlorate solution + 10 ml 0.0101 M 3-Cl-OHB + 20 ml dioxane.

Results and Discussion

The practical proton-ligand stability constant, log P_{K^H} of the ligand has been obtained as the Bjerrum half-integral value. The same has also been calculated at different points using the equation

$$\log P_{K^H} = B + \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1 - \bar{n}_H}$$

The average value of log P_{K^H} obtained by the point-wise calculation method is 11.24 ± 0.05 which is in excellent agreement with the half-integral value (11.24). It is interesting to consider this value together with those for 2-hydroxy-butyrophenone (12.32) and 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobutyrophenone (11.18) reported earlier⁷⁻⁸ and compare them with the corresponding values for salicylaldehyde derivatives⁹ since all these systems are similar and characterized by intramolecular hydrogen-bonding. Postmus et al.⁹ observed that the intramolecular hydrogen bond is weakened least by chloro substitution in 3-position of salicylaldehyde and most in the 5-position. Our results on 2-hydroxy-butyrophenone derivatives show that the 5-chloro-derivative is indeed a stronger acid compared to the 3-chloro-derivative, although the difference in log P_{K^H} values is not very

Fig. 1. Formation curves of bivalent metal complexes with 3ClOHB.

● \bar{n}_{calc}
○ \bar{n}_{obs}

large (~ 0.06 log unit). This might be attributed to the mesomeric effect of chloro-substitution in 5-position^{9,10} which would counteract the electronic effect partly and make the 5-chloro derivative a weaker acid than otherwise expected.

From the metal-ligand formation curves (Fig. 1), it can be seen that the maximum values of \bar{n} for Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) are more than 1, indicating that 1:1 and 1:2 complexes are formed. Log K_1 and log K_2 values have been determined by the least-squares¹¹ and linear-plot methods¹². To check the validity of K_1 and K_2 , these were substituted into the formation function for each system and formation curve for each system was calculated. It was observed that \bar{n}_{calc} showed good agreement (standard deviation ≈ 0.02) in systems involving Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) (vide Fig. 1).

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES WITH 3-CHLORO-2-HYDROXY-BUTYROPHENONE

	Temp. = $40^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$; $\mu \approx 0.1M(\text{NaClO}_4)$		
	Linear-plots	Least-squares	σ
Cu(II)			
log β_2	15.41	15.15	±0.037
log K_1	8.34	8.42	
log K_2	7.07	6.73	
Ni(II)			
log β_2	10.91	10.92	±0.020
log K_1	5.89	5.82	
log K_2	5.02	5.10	
Co(II)			
log β_2	11.53	11.51	±0.034
log K_1	5.85	5.85	
log K_2	5.68	5.66	

It can be seen (Table 1) that the order $\text{Cu} > \text{Co} > \text{Ni}$ of log K_1 values does not conform to the well established Irving-Williams order¹³. It is observed that positions of Ni and Co are reversed. However, the observed difference in log K_1 values for Ni and Co is small, so that the actual order is rendered uncertain. The reversal of position of cobalt and nickel is rather

difficult to account for, in absence of other information. It may be due to oxidation of Co(II) to Co(III) particularly in alkaline solution^{14,15}. This is strengthened by the fact that complexation in this system is observed to occur between $B \approx 6.5$ and 9.0.

In view of very low concentrations (4×10^{-4}) of the metal ions used in the titrations, formation of polynuclear complexes has been ignored. Titrations performed with different ratios of metal to ligand showed that the stability constant is independent of metal-ion concentrations.

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